

PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON PLAY-BASED LEARNING: MOTIVATIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Pre-Service Teachers' Perspectives on Play-Based Learning: Motivations and Opportunities

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Abstract

This study delves into the perspectives of pre-service teachers regarding play-based learning, focusing on motivations, and opportunities. Ten (10) Bachelor of Elementary Education pre-service teachers from Western Mindanao State University were interviewed using qualitative phenomenological research methods. Data collection involved one-on-one interviews, audio recordings, and thematic analysis. The demographic data revealed a diverse group of respondents in terms of teaching experience, grade levels taught, and gender distribution. The interview findings highlighted common themes among pre-service teachers regarding their perspectives on play-based learning such as effective approach, classroom practices, promotes positive experiences. Motivations for incorporating play-based learning included promoting holistic development, student centered learning, and fostering meaningful learning. Opportunities identified through play-based learning included learners' involvement, behavior management, and learning efficiency. Generally, the study underscores the positive impact of play-based learning on student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes, as perceived by pre-service teachers. The study recommends incorporating play-based learning strategies in education, providing professional development for educators, and conducting further research on its impact on academic performance and social skills.

Keywords: *pre-service teachers, play-based learning, perspectives, learning, student, opportunities, motivations*

Introduction

Play provides opportunities for young children to explore ideas, experiment with materials, and express new understandings. The play-based pedagogies are essential for providing learners with opportunities to learn counting, visualizing groups, and problem-solving skills. It emphasizes the importance of a hybrid approach, highlighting the need for alternative pathways to promote the implementation of play-based teaching strategies in the foundation phase (Ndlovu & Dumsani, 2021). Play-based learning has garnered considerable attention as an effective approach in early childhood and primary education, fostering holistic development and active engagement among young learners.

Moreover, play-based learning has contributed to 21st century learning skills targeting collaboration, creative and critical thinking language, social and emotional development as well as problem solving skills. Hence, parents and other state officials have become strict leading teachers to focus more on worksheets, direct instruction and memorization or sometimes called as didactic approach in learning (Parker et. al. 2022).

In addition, most educators employ traditional play since it has shaped the child's social interaction. Pre-service teachers are the ones who incorporate this the most because they are exposed to a wide range of pedagogical techniques, and how they view these approaches will have a huge impact on how they teach in the future. The successful implementation of the technique in the classroom can also be influenced by the understanding of the motivations and opportunities linked to play-based learning. This emphasizes the necessity of investigating, comprehending, and addressing the variables influencing pre-service teachers' perceptions on play-based learning. However, in the field of education, the exploration of innovative pedagogical approaches is important. This study was conducted in the Integrated Laboratory School (ILS) of Western Mindanao State University (WMSU) main campus. This study explores the perspectives of aspiring educators on play-based learning in primary education as society evolves to acknowledge the holistic development of young learners. It becomes essential to completely understand the motivations and opportunities that pre-service teachers see in play-based learning. For this reason, the researchers aimed to add to the existing knowledge by determining the perspectives of the pre-service teachers on play-based learning in terms of motivations and opportunities.

More so, despite the growing support for play-based learning, there's a lack of understanding about how the pre-service teachers perceive it. Knowing the views, motivations, and effective implementation strategies was vital as they were implemented in this approach. Many countries recognize the importance of play-based learning, so aligning the pre-service teachers' perspectives with this goal is crucial.

This research explored the motivations and opportunities perceived by pre-service teachers concerning play-based learning. By addressing this research gap, the study aimed to enhance teacher preparation programs, promote the effective implementation of play-based learning in classrooms, and contribute to the ongoing discourse surrounding elementary education. The study's overarching goal was to bridge the gap between research and practice, ultimately benefiting young learners and shaping the future of education.

Research Questions

This study determined the perspectives of the pre-service teachers on play-based learning in terms of motivations and opportunities. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the perspectives of pre-service teachers on play-based learning?
2. What motivates the pre-service teachers to use play-based learning in the teaching?
3. What opportunities does play-based learning present for fostering a holistic learning experience?

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a phenomenological qualitative research design to investigate the research topic to fully comprehend, define, and capture the essence of participants' encounters. It is a qualitative research method that focuses on exploring and understanding the lived experiences of individuals. It originated in philosophy and was later adapted for use in various disciplines, including psychology, sociology, and education.

According to the Global Market Intelligence and Research Manager, Good (2023), the goal of the phenomenological method is to explore and describe the essence of human experiences, attempting to bracket or set aside preconceived notions to approach phenomena with fresh eyes. It is concerned with the way individuals experience and make sense of the world. The focus is on obtaining rich, detailed descriptions rather than achieving statistical representativeness. This method also involves a systematic process to identify and understand the essential themes and structures of the lived experiences.

Participants

This study used purposive sampling in selecting respondents to attain precise answers in a one-on-one interview. The respondents of this study were the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) Pre-service Teachers of Western Mindanao State University (WMSU), who taught young learners from grades 1-6. There were ten (10) respondents who had been part of this study with the given research instrument. The participants had utilized a play-based approach as a teaching method for young learners and they are the most suitable respondents for data gathering.

Instrument

One-on-one interview was used with the respondents as a research instrument in this study. The research instrument included a series of questions that aimed of knowing the pre-service teachers' perspectives on the play-based approach, the experiences of pre-service teachers practicing to integrate the play-based approach, as well as the motivations and opportunities the play-based approach brought in the teaching field. There were nine (9) questions given to the respondents that sought to understand how play-based learning motivated pre-service teachers and what play-based learning was all about in the teaching field.

The validity of the semi-structured interview questions that the researchers constructed was subject for validation. The Western Mindanao State University College of Teacher Education's research specialists validated the instrument. The letter requesting permission to validate the research instrument distributed with a content validation sheet.

The semi-structured interview developed by the researchers was the subject of the reliability test. This underwent a reliability test, which was done through pilot testing. The pilot testing was intended to ensure that the procedures and techniques used for this study's data collection were appropriate and consistent. Three (3) Pre-service Teachers in Bachelor of Elementary Education had volunteered to participate in the pilot testing.

Procedure

This study employed a qualitative research method to thoroughly explore pre-service teachers' perspectives on play-based learning: motivations and opportunities.

Ten (10) BEED pre-service teachers of Western Mindanao State University (WMSU) Integrated Laboratory School (ILS) were interviewed in one-on-one to collect the data. Before the interview, a letter of permission to conduct the study was given to the Dean of the College of Teacher Education. Before conducting the interview, the researchers obtained the respondents' consent and informed them of the benefits, risks, and confidentiality of their answers. The pre-service teachers were asked nine (9) questions by the researchers during the one-on-one interview to gather data. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the information gathered from the one-on-one interview with 10 BEED pre-service teachers at the Integrated Laboratory School of Western Mindanao State University. Future steps involved identifying recurrent themes and patterns in the responses of participants, allowing a comprehensive exploration of pre-service teachers' perspectives on play-based learning in terms of motivations and opportunities. The analysis allowed researchers to generate conclusions, findings, and recommendations.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the ten (10) respondents, tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly. To interpret the data gathered, this study used thematic analysis. It is a method of analyzing qualitative data. It had been usually applied to a set of texts, such as interviews or transcripts. There have been various approaches to conducting thematic analysis, but the most common form follows a six-step process: familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up. Following

this process also helped avoid confirmation bias when formulating the analysis (Caulfield, 2022).

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to fundamental ethical standards for research. The manuscript had been provided to the WMSU Research Ethics Committee Review Board for complete approval to request permission to conduct the study. Precautions had been implemented to prevent any harm to participants during and after the interviews. The participants did not receive any incentives or compensation during the entire duration of the study. Identities were kept confidential and only used in the research context. Personal information was not disclosed without the participant's consent during the interview. Before the interview process and all related proceedings, the researchers had asked for the participant's permission to audio-record the session.

Results and Discussion

This study aimed to delve into the teachers' perspectives on play-based learning focusing on motivations and opportunities. This chapter shows the demographic data of the respondents, data-collection procedure, and analysis and emerging inferences which involved management of the data, proof of collected data findings, data analysis and emerging themes, and a section on how the findings address the research questions.

Table 1. *Demographic Data of the Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Teaching period incorporating PBL</i>	<i>Grade level assigned</i>	<i>Gender</i>
PST 1	1.5 year	Grades 4	Male
PST 2	1 month	Grades 4	Female
PST 3	1 month	Grade 4	Female
PST 4	1 month	Grade 4	Female
PST 5	1 month	Grade 4	Female
PST 6	1.5 years	Grade 2	Female
PST 7	1 month	Grade 4	Female
PST 8	1 month	Grade 4	Female
PST 9	1.5 years	Grade 1	Female
PST 10	1 month	Grade 4	Female

Table 1 provides a summary of the respondents' demographic data. Respondents were all pre-service teachers in one of the integrated laboratory schools in Zamboanga City. They differ from the teaching period incorporating play-based learning, where seven pre-service teachers (PST 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10) have been incorporating play-based learning in their teaching for about 1 month and the other three respondents (PST 1, 6, 9) were incorporating play-based learning in their teaching for about one and a half year.

In terms of grade level that they are assigned to, eight pre-service teachers (PST 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10) have taught grade 4 learners and one pre-service teacher (PST 6) has taught grade 2 learners, and the other one (PST 9) has taught grade 1 learners. In terms of their Gender, most of the PSTs (PST 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10) were Female and only one PST (PST 1) was Male.

Interview Findings

This study aimed to determine the perspectives of the pre-service teachers on play-based learning in terms of motivations and opportunities. The responses of the respondents were transcribed, and themes were drawn and presented along with the research questions. Ten (10) pre-service teachers were interviewed for this purpose.

Interview Question 1. What is your perspective about play-based learning?

Pre-service Teachers' Responses

All pre-service teachers agree that play-based learning is a beneficial strategy for engaging students, promoting active learning, and enhancing motivation, particularly for young learners. They also emphasize the importance of effective classroom management.

"Play-based learning is effective and engaging in an active classroom." PST 1 and 2

"Effective management is crucial in play-based learning to handle misbehavior." PST 3 and 4

"Incorporating games and fun elements helps engage students not interested in traditional methods." PST 5 and 6

"Play-based learning, especially for young learners, makes the learning process more effective." PST 7 and 8

"Well-executed play-based learning is highly engaging and beneficial for students' motivation and learning outcomes." PST 9 and 10

According to the pre-service teachers, play-based learning (PBL) is considered an effective and engaging strategy for promoting active learning and enhancing student motivation. Effective classroom management was also crucial in handling misbehavior during PBL. Incorporating games and fun elements could help engage students who were not interested in traditional methods. Overall, well-

executed play- based learning was highly beneficial for students' motivation and learning outcomes (PST 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10).

Researchers' Reflection

Based on the perspectives shared by the pre-service teachers, it was evident that there was a consensus on the effectiveness and applicability of play- based learning in engaging students promoting active learning, and enhancing motivation, particularly for young learners. They emphasized the importance of effective management and the incorporation of games and fun elements to engage students. They also recognized the effectiveness of play- based learning, especially for young learners, in achieving positive learning outcomes. Overall, the researchers concluded that play-based learning, when combined with effective classroom management, could create engaging and effective learning experiences for students.

Interview Question 2. Have you ever used a play-based strategy in your teaching? How often?

Pre-service Teachers' Responses

The pre-service teachers commonly utilized play-based strategies in their teaching, incorporating them throughout lessons or specific sections to engage students, enhance learning, and create an enjoyable classroom environment.

"I incorporate play-based learning throughout different parts of the lesson, but sometimes only in specific sections to maintain lesson quality..." PST 1

"Interactive games are often included in lesson plans, especially during the application phase." PST 2

"I have been integrating play-based learning since the beginning of my teaching, as I've observed that students learn best when they are playing..." PST 3

"I incorporate play-based strategies in lessons that require active engagement, such as 'pass the ball' for question answering." PST 4

"Using play-based strategies ignites excitement and interest in the subject among students." PST 5

"I frequently incorporate play-based learning, especially when using a deductive approach, to ensure effective learning and enjoyment." PST 6

"Play-based or game-based strategies are particularly effective, especially when working with numbers." PST 7

"Currently, we often incorporate play-based strategies, especially during group activities." PST 8

"Play-based learning is often used during group activities, particularly in our Mapeh subject." PST 9

"When using play-based learning, it is important to manage and control student behavior." PST 10

Pre-service teachers commonly incorporate play-based strategies in their teaching to engage students, enhance learning, and create an enjoyable classroom environment. They utilized play-based learning throughout lessons or specific sections, incorporating interactive games and activities to maintain lesson quality and promote active engagement. Pre-service teachers observed that play-based learning ignites excitement, interest, and effective learning, especially when working with numbers or during group activities. Managing and controlling student behavior was considered important when implementing play-based learning (PST 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10).

Researcher's Reflection

The researchers reflected on the pre-service teachers' responses regarding the use of play-based strategies in their teaching. The majority of the pre-service teachers have incorporated play-based learning in their classrooms. They emphasized the importance of maintaining lesson quality while integrating play-based strategies throughout different parts of the lesson. Interactive games were often included, particularly during the application phase. The pre-service teachers recognized that students learn best when they are engaged in play and that play-based strategies ignite excitement and interest. They frequently utilized play-based learning, especially when using a deductive approach. The effectiveness of play- based or game-based strategies, particularly with numbers, is also acknowledged. Group activities and the Mapeh subject are common contexts for implementing play-based learning. The pre-service teachers emphasized the importance of managing and controlling student behavior during play-based activities. Overall, the researchers concluded that incorporating play-based strategies enhances student engagement, learning outcomes, and enjoyment in the classroom.

Interview Question 3. How do you feel about using play-based learning in your teaching?

Pre-service Teachers' Responses

The pre-service teachers expressed positive feelings towards incorporating play-based learning, highlighting the fulfillment, enjoyment, and joy. They also acknowledged the need for effective management to ensure student behavior and focused during game- based activities.

“It’s fulfilling to see students having fun while learning in my subject.” PST 2

“It’s enjoyable to see learners play and learn simultaneously, moving away from traditional pen and paper tasks.” PST 4

“I feel happy using play-based learning as it brings joy to see students enjoying themselves while learning.” PST 6

“I feel okay incorporating play-based learning, but it requires careful management to maintain student behavior and focus.” PST 7

“I feel happy when students enjoy games, as it allows me to reward them.” PST 8

“We enjoyed teaching and seeing our students learn while enjoying the game.” PST 9

Pre-service teachers expressed positive feelings towards incorporating play-based learning, finding fulfillment and enjoyment in seeing students have fun while learning. It brought joy to students and teachers as they move away from traditional tasks and witnessed students enjoying themselves during game-based activities. Effective management was acknowledged as essential for maintaining student behavior and focused during play-based learning (PST 2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9).

Researchers’ Reflection

The researchers reflected on the positive sentiments expressed by the pre-service teachers incorporating play-based learning in their teaching. They appreciated the common themes of fulfillment, enjoyment, and joy that arose from witnessing students have fun while learning through play. The researchers also noted the acknowledgment of the respondents on the importance of effective management during game-based activities. Overall, the researchers found the responses affirming to the positive impact of play-based learning on student engagement and enjoyment in the classroom. They concluded that incorporating play-based strategies, along with appropriate management techniques, contributed to a more fulfilling and effective teaching experience for both educators and students.

Interview Question 4. What motivates you to incorporate play-based learning?

Pre-service Teachers’ Responses

The common motivation among the respondents is the desire to engage students, make learning enjoyable, and meet their diverse needs. They recognize the importance of capturing students’ attention, adjusting teaching methods, and utilizing play-based learning to enhance student motivation and participation.

“To motivate students and make the lesson enjoyable.” PST 1 “Previous experiences and positive student reactions motivate me to use play-based teaching.” PST 2

“The students themselves, as play-based learning increases engagement and participation.” PST 3

“Adjusting teaching to match student interests and gain their attention.” PST 4

“Preventing student boredom and meeting their needs.” PST 5

“The natural inclination of children to play and the need to capture their attention.” PST 6

“Motivated by young children’s desire to play games and mentor recommendations.” PST 7

“Engaging students and addressing boredom through games and active participation.” PST 8

“Benefiting learners’ motor skills and catering to their love for play.” PST 9

“Allowing children to learn through play and experience interactive learning.” PST 10

It is coming from the PST 1, PST 3, PST 4, PST 6, PST 7, PST 8, and PST 10 that PBL can engage and motivate the students while PST 2 said that it is based on teaching experiences, while PST 5 and PST 9 said that PBL can develop learners’ skills.

Researchers’ Reflection

The researchers observed that the pre-service teachers shared a common motivation to engage students, make learning enjoyable, and meet their diverse needs through play-based learning. They recognized the importance of capturing students’ attention and adjusting teaching methods accordingly. The teachers valued the natural inclination of children to play and the benefits it provided to their motor skills development. Positive student reactions and mentor recommendations also influenced their motivation to incorporate play-based teaching. Overall, the researchers concluded that play-based learning effectively engaged students, made learning enjoyable, and catered to their individual needs.

Interview Question 5. Why do you incorporate play-based learning in your teaching?

Pre-service Teachers’ Responses

The common motivation among the respondents is to engage and motivate students, make learning enjoyable, and cater to their diverse needs through play-based learning. They recognized the effectiveness of this approach in capturing students’ attention, enhancing

participation, and facilitating a more meaningful learning experience.

“To motivate students, accommodate all of them, and enhance their psychomotor skills.” PST 1

“To engage students who may not be interested in listening to traditional teaching methods.” PST 2

“To effectively engage students and encourage their participation.” PST 3

“To gain students’ interest and understand their preferences through different game varieties.” PST 4

“To entertain and make learning enjoyable, especially for topics that may be perceived as boring.” PST 5

“To effectively teach elementary students who are naturally inclined to play and capture their attention.” PST 6

“To motivate and energize lower-grade students through game- based learning, particularly in English language acquisition.” PST 7

“To effectively teach MAPEH subjects and facilitate easier comprehension through play-based integration.” PST 8

“To motivate students and facilitate learning through various teaching strategies.” PST 10

This is coming from PST 1, PST 6, PST 7, and PST 10 that PBL motivates the student’s participation while PST 2, PST 3, and PST 5 says that PBL is use to engage and catch the attention of students. PST 4 says that PBL gains the interest of students while PST 8 says that PBL facilitates in easier comprehension when it comes to MAPEH subjects. Researchers’ Reflection

The researchers reflected on the pre-service teachers’ motivations for incorporating play-based learning in their teaching. They observed a shared desire to engage and motivate students, make learning enjoyable, and cater to their diverse needs. The teachers recognized the effectiveness of play-based learning in capturing students’ attention and enhancing participation. Overall, the researchers concluded that incorporating play- based strategies effectively engaged students and enhanced the learning experience.

Interview Question 6. In which part of your lesson do you incorporate the play-based learning? How?

Pre-service Teachers’ Responses

The pre-service teachers commonly incorporated play-based learning in the motivation and application parts of their lessons. They used various activities and strategies, such as passing a ball, using props like a mystery box, and engaging students in group activities. The aim is to enhance motivation, engage students, and make the learning experience more interactive and enjoyable.

“In the motivation part, application part, and evaluation.

For example, using a ball to pass around and answer questions related to the topic.” PST 1

“In the inductive method during application or presentation, and in the deductive method. Also in the reading part during application.” PST 2

“Particularly in the presentation and application parts, using activities like ‘fact or bluff’ and the mystery box.” PST 3

“Primarily in the application part, and sometimes in the motivation part with mini activities.” PST 4

“Sometimes during drills or group activities, often in the application part.” PST 5

“Mainly to enhance motivation and capture learners’ attention, can be used in the application part.” PST 6

“Depends on the subject matter, such as using art gallery or a mystery box during math or Mapeh lessons.” PST 7

“In the motivation and application parts, following the 4A’s framework.” PST 8

“During group activities and physical education (PE) time.”

PST 9

“Mostly in the application part, but can also be in the motivation part with activity-based learning.” PST 10

This is coming from PST 1, PST 3, PST 4, PST 5, PST 8, and PST 10 they incorporate PBL in the motivation and application part because group activities are applicable there that can engage students and capture learners’ attention while PST 2 says that it depends on what kind of lesson plan method and PST 7 says that it depends on the subject matter.

Researchers’ Reflection

The researchers reflected on the pre-service teachers’ common practices of incorporating play-based learning in the motivation and application parts of their lessons. They observed that various activities and strategies, such as passing a ball, using props like a mystery box, and engaging students in group activities, were utilized to enhance motivation and make the learning experience more interactive and enjoyable. The researchers found these approaches effective in capturing learners’ attention and promoting engagement.

Interview Question 7. What opportunities can you get in incorporating play-based learning?

Pre-service Teachers' Responses

The pre-service teachers commonly identified opportunities such as connecting with students, gaining their attention and enthusiasm, improving teaching skills, and facilitating student learning through play-based approaches. They also highlighted the benefits of creating an enjoyable learning environment and understanding students' characteristics and interests.

"Connecting with students and interacting with them to answer their questions." PST 1

"Getting students' attention, winning their hearts, and creating excitement and eagerness to learn." PST 2

"Improving teaching skills and meeting students' interests and engagement." PST 3

"Creating a fun and enjoyable learning environment, where students realize that schooling is not just about stress but also about learning." PST 5

"Monitoring students' attitudes and helping them learn how to control their behavior." PST 6

"Providing opportunities for socialization, using technology, and incorporating multimedia games." PST 8

"Improving teaching skills and facilitating student learning through play-based approaches." PST 9

"Learning by doing and discovering different strategies through play-based learning." PST 10

This is coming from PST 1, 2, and 3 they get student interactive and make learning engaging, while PST 5 and 6 states that play is fun and help them manage student behavior. Meanwhile PST 8, 9, 10 it promotes socialization and improves their teaching skills and strategies.

Researchers' Reflection

The researchers reflected on the common opportunities identified by the pre-service teachers when using play-based learning. They observed that the teachers recognized the potential for connecting with students, capturing their attention, and fostering enthusiasm for learning. The researchers also noted the emphasis on improving teaching skills, meeting students' interests, and creating a fun learning environment.

Additionally, the researchers found that play-based learning provided opportunities for understanding students' characteristics, promoting socialization, and facilitating student learning.

Interview Question 8. How do you describe the learning behavior of the learners when incorporating play-based learning?

Pre-service Teachers' Responses

The pre-service teachers commonly described the learning behavior of learners when incorporating play-based learning as active, engaged, and sometimes chaotic. They recognized the need for behavior management strategies to ensure a positive learning environment.

"Active engagement and participation when play-based learning is used." PST 3

"Mixed behavior, with play-based learning helping even naughty students answer and emphasizing the need for behavior management." PST 4

"Varied behavior, with some students showing interest and others being stubborn, requiring facilitation and rules." PST 5

"Happy and excited behavior, but with the potential for rowdiness and chaos, necessitating clear standards and reinforcement of rules." PST 6

"Behavior depends on classroom management, with potential for both positive and negative outcomes." PST 7

"Eager, excited, and sometimes chaotic behavior." PST 9 "Excitement and eagerness, requiring behavior management." PST 10

Coming from the responses of 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10, the behavior of the students varied as some of them got excited, and some got chaotic but manageable when classroom management was incorporated.

Researchers' Reflection

The researchers reflected on the common descriptions provided by the pre-service teachers regarding the learning behavior of learners when incorporating play-based learning. They observed that learners were commonly described as active, engaged, and sometimes exhibiting chaotic behavior.

The researchers recognized the importance of implementing behavior management strategies to maintain a positive learning

environment. They also acknowledged the potential for both positive and negative outcomes depending on effective classroom management. Overall, the researchers concluded that play-based learning can elicit eager and excited behavior from learners, but clear standards and reinforcement of rules are necessary to address any potential challenges that may arise.

Interview Question 9. What makes play-based learning an effective approach in primary learners?

Pre-service Teachers’ Responses

The pre-service teachers commonly highlighted that play-based learning was effective for primary learners because it addresses their short attention spans and increases engagement through enjoyable and meaningful activities. They recognized the importance of capturing students’ attention and making the learning process more engaging to enhance their understanding and retention of the lessons.

“Addressing the short attention span of primary learners and helping them focus on the lesson.” PST 3

“Making the topic or lesson more meaningful and memorable for primary learners, leveraging their natural inclination to play.” PST 6

“Capturing the attention of young learners with short attention spans, making the learning process more engaging.” PST 7

“Addressing the short attention span of primary learners and increasing their focus through enjoyable play-based learning activities.” PST 9

This is coming from the response of PST 3, 6, 7, and 9, they say that play-based learning gets their students more focused as a sign of efficacy integrating it during the lesson.

Researchers’ Reflection

The researchers reflected on the common reasons provided by the pre- service teachers regarding the effectiveness of play-based learning for primary learners. They observed that play-based learning effectively addressed the short attention spans of primary learners and increased engagement through enjoyable and meaningful activities.

The researchers recognized the importance of capturing students’ attention and making the learning process more engaging to enhance their understanding and retention of the lessons. They concluded that play-based learning leveraged the natural inclination of primary learners to play, making the topics or lessons more meaningful and memorable. Overall, the researchers acknowledged the positive impact of play- based learning on primary learners’ attention, engagement, and learning outcomes.

Emergent Themes and Codes

According to Elliott, V. (2018), coding is usually a general process in a qualitative study, thereby researchers break down data accordingly to produce new ideas and are considered a fundamental aspect of the analytical process of coding the data. During the one-on-one interview of the ten (10) respondents, the data were transcribed arranged, and manually coded or categorized.

The transcribed data were broken down or sorted to generate the themes thereby eliminating fillers and pauses of the respondents but taking up the data. The emerging themes from the analyzed interview transcripts were;

Table 2. Emergent Theme for Statement of the Problem 1

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
Effective Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Effectiveness • Student Engagement • Classroom Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student Engagement • Active learning • Enhanced motivation • Classroom management and handling misbehavior • Incorporating games and fun elements • Student motivation and learning outcomes
Classroom Practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive Games in Lesson Plans • Group Activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enjoyable classroom environment • Active engagement and learning enhancement • Igniting excitement and interest in the subject
Promotes Positive Experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enjoyment • Student Behavior 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive feelings • Effective management of student behavior and focus • Moving away from traditional tasks • Rewarding students for enjoying games

Relationship of Interview Responses to Research Question 1:

Statement of the problem 1: What are the perspectives of Pre-service teachers on play-based learning?

Figure 1. Themes of Research Question 1

Relationship of Theme 1. Effective Approach

The Pre-service teachers agreed that play-based learning effectively engages students, promotes active learning, and enhances motivation, particularly for young learners. They emphasized the importance of effective management and incorporating games and fun elements to engage students. They also recognize the positive impact of play-based learning on achieving favorable learning outcomes. This highlighted the relationship between play-based learning and classroom dynamics.

Learning Effectiveness

Play-based learning was a beneficial strategy for engaging students, promoting active learning, and enhancing motivation, particularly for young learners. They also emphasized the importance of effective classroom management. The study emphasized the potential advantages of integrating game elements into the learning process, which can lead to increased student participation.

“... effective and engaging in an active classroom.” PST 1 and 2

“Effective management is crucial ... to handle misbehavior.” PST 3 and 4

“Incorporating games and fun elements helps engage students ...” PST 5 and 6

“... makes the learning process more effective.” PST 7 and 8

“...highly engaging and beneficial for students’ motivation and learning outcomes.” PST 9 and 10

According to Mavridis (2020), the study explores the implementation of play-based learning in education and its influence on learning outcomes. It highlights the beneficial effects of utilizing games to promote student engagement and enhance educational results.

Moreover, the play-based learning approach was an effective method to stimulate student engagement in learning, as well as to integrate literature on the play-based learning technique for educational objectives (Almulla, 2020).

Additionally, play-based learning was an essential component of primary education, offering children a significant and pleasurable method to learn and discover their surroundings. Instead of traditional teaching techniques that depend on memorization and repeated exercises, play-based learning activities enable children to participate in practical experiences that spark their imagination, inquisitiveness, and problem-solving abilities (Arhin, 2023).

Student Engagement

The play-based learning is a beneficial strategy for engaging students and enhancing motivation. According to Nacional (2023), the study explores the effectiveness of using gamification in education as a means to enhance student engagement and motivation. The research delves into the impact of integrating game elements and interactive learning technologies within the classroom setting. Here are the exact responses about student engagement and motivation:

“...is engaging in an active classroom.” PST 1 and 2 “... helps engage students not interested in traditional methods.” PST 5 and 6

“Well-executed... highly engaging and beneficial for students’...” PST 9 and 10

The incorporation of play-based in education has the potential to increase students’ levels of engagement, similar to the way games can enhance their specific skills and optimize their learning. Gamification can also provide immediate feedback, personalized challenges, and a sense of achievement, which further enhances students’ motivation and encourages them to continue learning. (Smiderle, et. al. 2020).

Moreover, play-based learning was an effective approach utilized to boost motivation and engagement in programming classes among students. This strategy not only enhances their motivation to learn but also fosters a deeper understanding of programming principles and problem- solving skills (Hellin, et. al. 2023).

Classroom Management

Effective classroom management was crucial in play-based learning, especially when it comes to handling misbehavior. Here are the exact responses about classroom management and behavior:

“Effective management is crucial ... to handle misbehavior.” PST 3 and 4

This response highlighted the importance of effective classroom management in play-based learning. Haverback et al. (2023) developed and validated a standardized rating instrument in their study, which examines effective classroom management in primary education.

Additionally, the role of a teacher in primary education goes beyond delivering curriculum outcomes. Teachers are responsible for equipping students with the necessary tools for social and academic success, both inside and outside the classroom.

This includes effective classroom management techniques and promoting positive behavior, creating a safe and inclusive learning environment (Franklin, 2020).

Relationship of Theme 2. Classroom Practices

The Pre-service teachers commonly incorporated play-based learning in their classrooms, integrating strategies throughout lessons while maintaining lesson quality. Interactive games are included, particularly during the application phase. They recognized the effectiveness of play-based learning in engaging students and igniting excitement.

Play-based approaches are frequently used, especially with a deductive approach or in subjects like Mapeh. The teachers emphasized managing student behavior during play-based activities.

Interactive Games in Lesson Plans

The pre-service teachers commonly utilized play-based strategies, including the incorporation of interactive games, in their lesson plans. Interactive games are often included during the application phase of the lesson.

Play-based strategies are incorporated to promote active engagement and effective learning, such as using “pass the ball” for question answering. These strategies are particularly effective when working with numbers and are frequently used during group activities. Overall, the use of play-based and game-based strategies in lesson plans is seen as beneficial for both effective learning and enjoyment.

“...often included in lesson plans... application phase.” PST 2

“...in lessons that require active engagement, such as ‘pass the ball’ ...” PST 4

Furthermore, teachers recognized the benefits of incorporating interactive games in lesson plans. These games enhanced student engagement, promote knowledge acquisition, and create memorable learning experiences. Interactive games provide hands-on exploration, problem-solving opportunities, and critical thinking exercises. (Jääskä & Aaltonen, 2022).

Moreover, gaming has underwent significant advancements, to the extent that it is now employed as an educational tool across various disciplines to instruct students. These games served as engaging and interactive mediums that facilitate active participation and effective learning. These games were carefully designed to align with the developmental needs and learning objectives of young learners, fostering their cognitive, social, and emotional growth (Karagiorgas & Niemann, 2020).

Group Activities

The play-based strategies were commonly utilized during group activities in their teaching. They find that incorporating play-based learning during group activities enhances student engagement, promotes active learning, and creates an enjoyable learning environment. Specifically, play-based learning was often used in the Mapeh subject.

However, it was important for teachers to effectively manage and control student behavior when implementing play-based learning approaches during group activities. Overall, the use of play-based strategies during group activities was seen as beneficial for student learning and participation.

“.. we often incorporate ... especially during group activities.” PST 8

“... often used during group activities, particularly in our Mapah subject.” PST 9

According to Danniels & Pyle (2022). In play-based kindergarten programs, teachers ensure that children’s learning and development goals are nurtured through play. Group activities in Early Education play a crucial role in promoting social interaction, collaboration, and communication skills among young learners.

Relationship of Theme 3. Promotes Positive Experiences

The Pre-service teachers valued the integration of play-based learning in their teaching, recognizing the themes of fulfillment, enjoyment, and joy that arise from seeing students have fun while learning through play.

They also emphasized the importance of effective management during game-based activities. This highlighted the relationship between positive experiences and effective management in play-based learning.

Enjoyment

Incorporating play-based learning in teaching brought positive emotions and enjoyment for both students and teachers. The pre-service teachers found fulfillment and happiness when they see students having fun while learning and actively engaging in the subject. They enjoy witnessing learners move away from traditional tasks and enjoy the process of playing and learning simultaneously.

The pre-service teachers also expressed joy and a sense of reward when students engaged in games and found it enjoyable to learn while having fun. This positive atmosphere contributed to a more enjoyable teaching and learning experience overall.

“... students having fun while learning ...” PST 2 “It’s enjoyable to see learners play and learn simultaneously ...” PST 4

“... it brings joy to see students enjoying themselves...” PST 6

“... students enjoy games....” PST 8

“... seeing our students learn while enjoying the game.” PST 9

According to the study of Mustafina et al.,(2020), teachers can influence emotionally on their students' engagement in learning, their actions and words can have a big impact on the learners’ performance and can reflect on the mood of the learners. Through play-based learning, children could show positive emotions as they learn and the teacher boosts their confidence to incorporate different activities on how their learners react.

Student Behavior

The pre-service teacher acknowledged the importance of effective management in ensuring student behavior and focus during play-based learning activities. While play-based learning brings fulfillment, enjoyment, and joy to both students and teachers, the respondent recognized the need for careful management to maintain student behavior and focus.

The pre-service teachers understand that implementing effective management strategies was crucial in creating a productive learning environment during play-based activities.

“I feel okay....but it requires careful management to maintain student behavior and focus” PST 7

“it’s okay, it’s just you really need to manage or control the behavior of the students ...” PST10

Play was a valuable asset in children’s development, offering benefits such as enhancing learning abilities, advancing socio-psychological skills, and building self-concept. Effective management and student behavior are crucial for creating a conducive learning environment (Khalil, et. al. 2022).

Table 3. *Emergent Theme for Statement of the Problem 2*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
Promotes Holistic Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differentiated activities Skills development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging students Learners’ development Teaching experiences Students Diversity
Promotes Student- Centered Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced Student Participation Learning strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourage participation Enhance skills Make learning enjoyable Learning method
Fosters Meaningful Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivation and Application Adaptation to Subject Matter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivation, application, and evaluation Inductive method during presentation part

Relationship of Interview Responses to Research Question 2:

Statement of the problem 2: What motivates the pre-service teachers to use play-based learning in their teaching?

Figure 2. Themes of Research Question 2 Relationship of Theme 1. Promotes Holistic Development

The pre-service teachers agreed that play-based learning has the advantage of fostering a child's holistic development making a play-based approach to learning essential most especially in engaging the students by introducing the topic and having them participate in class discussion. Through unlocking the related concepts of this teaching approach empowering play-based strategy was an advantage to pre-service teachers to develop the well-being of a child.

Differentiated Activities

Fundamentally, differentiation involved tailoring instruction to accommodate varying learning styles, abilities, interests, and readiness levels. On the other hand, inclusion revolved around creating an environment where every learner feels valued, respected, and supported, irrespective of differences in background, ability, or identity. Some Pre-Service teachers agreed that using play-based learning can address the diverse needs and abilities of learners.

"Maybe to motivate the students as they don't grasp the topic." PST 1

"The students. The students itself. As what I've said earlier, they are diverse". PST 3

"Maybe in a way that it catches the attention of the students." PST 4

"Of course, our students, because, you know, they need that". PST 5

"...when I see young children wants to play games." PST 7

According to Trinanda and Yaswinda (2022), differentiated learning can help recognize the different abilities and skills of the learners. It shows the diversity of the learners according to their strengths, interests, and readiness. It can address the diverse needs and abilities that the learners might have, and teachers can use different methods, materials, and other strategies including the play-based approach to accommodate each learner's needs. Additionally, according to Astuti and Afendi (2022), play is a great way to give children a way to showcase their creativity and develop an interest in learning. It is important to foster the potential of the child at a young age as they explore their environment and learn new things. Through playing, the learners will be able to adapt to new things in their environment, and as they continue to explore and try new things, they will become curious.

Skills development

Holistic learning environment help recognize/promote unique strengths, interests, and learning styles of individuals, tailoring experiences to support personalized skill development. Some Pre-service teachers agreed that play-based learning can develop the different domains of the child. This environment integrated various disciplines, promoting a deeper understanding of subjects and encouraging learners to draw connections between different areas of knowledge.

"...play-based learning is helpful most especially in our learners as it develops their motor skills". PST 9

"...It motivates us to let the children learn or experience learning through playing not just on giving or feeding them information." PST 10

According to Taylor and Boyer (2019), play-based learning can develop different domains that the child could have, which include physical, mental, social, emotional, and language development. It can enhance the abilities of the learners and boost their interest through engaging and developmentally appropriate practices. Through play, the child could develop their skills as they continue to move and think critically, as well as love what they are doing.

Moreover, according to the study of Boryga (2023), play can boost the engagement of the child in learning as they naturally cultivate their enjoyment, including their interest as they are motivated to do the task. With the help and guidance of the teacher, the learners will be able to engage in learning while playing, and different activities can make them more active and catch their attention.

Relationship of Theme 2. Promotes Student-Centered Learning

The pre-service teachers incorporated play-based learning into their teaching practices as a means to create engaging and interactive educational experiences. This integration aligned with the principles of student-centered learning, emphasizing differentiation activities and skills development. By incorporating play-based learning, pre-service teachers were able to tailor activities to accommodate diverse learning styles and readiness levels among students, fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Enhanced Student Participation

Pre-service teachers stated that class discussions become more engaging and students become more participative when they incorporate play-based learning. Encouraging students' participation provides timely feedback and fosters positive environment so that students can feel motivated and belong as it also promotes interaction with their peers making learning a conducive learning process for both students and teachers. Through this strategy Pre-service teachers can cultivate an interactive learning environment and overall academic success.

"... motivate students, accommodate all of them, and enhance their psychomotor skills." PST 1

"... engage students who may not be interested in listening to traditional teaching methods." PST 2

"... effectively engage students and encourage their participation." PST 3

"... motivate and energize lower-grade students ..." PST 5

"... entertain and make learning enjoyable, ..." PST 7

"... naturally inclined to play and capture their attention." PST 8

According to Parker et. Al. (2019) playful experiences lead to deeper learning when they are joyful, actively engaging, meaningful, iterative, and socially interactive as students participate in their pre-service teachers' discussion. Moreover, the lay definition of play is to "engage in an activity for enjoyment or recreation rather than a serious purpose" (Oxford University Press, 2020).

According to research, they found that children who engaged in play-based learning activities had better memory recall and were able to sustain their attention for longer periods. Play-based learning has been shown to foster higher levels of motivation and engagement in children compared to traditional learning activities (McArdle, 2024).

Additionally, learners will be more productive, engaged, and excited about learning new things when the environment accommodates their needs and supports the learning outcomes (Padayichie, 2022). When play-based learning was increased motivation, self-confidence was enhanced (Vaisarova, 2022). As stated by the researchers, considering the learning environment of the students helps them be more engaged in the topic of the course through the help of a play-based approach.

Learning Strategies

The utilization of a play-based learning strategy leverages learners' natural curiosity, creativity, and motivation to enhance the learning process. Learners are encouraged to actively engage with concepts, materials, and issues through dynamic activities including games, exploration, and imaginative play, which promotes deeper learning and information retention.

Play-based learning encourages the development of critical thinking, communication, and teamwork by giving students the chance to engage in practical exploration, problem-solving, and social engagement. All things considered, play-based learning makes learning an engaging and happy process that promotes exploration, discovery, and significant learning objectives.

"... gain students' interest and understand their preferences ..." PST 6

"... effectively teach MAPEH subjects and facilitate easier comprehension ..." PST 10

A study by Allee-Herndon (2021) shows that including purposeful play, can contribute dramatically to improved language, literacy, and mathematics competencies and improved responses to kindergarten learning. Furthermore, play-based learning can be used as a tool to support academic learning, helping children to better understand and retain information (Hei Schools 2023). This enables the pre-service teachers to enhance the skills of the students in different learning areas using this strategy.

Relationship of Theme 3. Fosters Meaningful Learning

The data shows that Pre-service teachers are encouraged to incorporate play-based learning into their lessons by showcasing how successful it is at increasing student engagement, supporting holistic development, and enabling deeper knowledge of subjects. Pre-service teachers are motivated to use play-based learning as a pedagogical technique when they observe personally the beneficial effects it has on students’ motivation, creativity, and critical thinking abilities. Furthermore, seeing the excitement and enjoyment that students display during play-based activities helps pre-service teachers believe that this method works and motivates them to use it to create engaging and productive learning environments.

Motivation and Application

The incorporation of play-based learning into teaching methods, whether inductive or deductive, has a significant impact on the motivation of pre-service teachers. Pre-service teachers who experience the effectiveness of play-based learning within these methodological frameworks are motivated by its ability to enhance student engagement, foster critical thinking, and promote active participation in the learning process. The integration of play-based learning into both inductive and deductive teaching methods motivates pre-service teachers by providing them with innovative and effective strategies for creating dynamic and meaningful learning experiences that support the diverse needs and interests of their students.

“... in the motivation part, application part, and evaluation...” PST 1

“... in the inductive method during application or presentation, and in the deductive method. Also, in the reading part during application...” PST 2

“... particularly in the presentation and application parts, ...” PST 3

“... primarily in the application part, and sometimes in the motivation part ...” PST 4

“... sometimes during drills or group activities, often in the application part...” PST 5

“... can be used in the application part.” PST 6

“Mostly in the application part, but can also be in the motivation part ...” PST 10

Renard (2020) says that engaging energizer activities, is also considered as motivation activities for students. Students can relax and take an interactive break. It will clear their minds and motivate them to stay focused for the next hour. The application lesson is a type of learning instruction that gives the learners the opportunity to relate, express and apply what they have learned (Knoji 2011).

Adaptation to Subject Matter

Adapting a play-based approach in the teaching and learning process served as a great motivator especially to pre-service teachers as it is tailored to the specific subject areas when they demonstrate teaching in the classroom. They are inspired to incorporate this approach into their lessons as a means of enhancing student engagement and comprehension. Pre-service teachers believed that by integrating play-based learning into teaching they are more likely to be seamlessly incorporated in various subjects such as MAPEH, math, science, and other subject areas. This adaptability not only motivates pre-service teachers by providing them with innovative teaching strategies but also empowers them to address diverse learning styles and interests among their students.

“... using art gallery or a mystery box during math or Mapeh lessons.” PST 7

“... during group activities and physical education (PE) time.” PST 9

According to Kleim et.al. (2019), adaptive learning support includes both the support provided during a learning situation and the preparation for and reflection after the provision of the support. This approach ensures that learners receive continuous and tailored assistance throughout their learning journey. As the learning process continued, they offered timely support, adjusting their approach based on individual progress and feedback. Furthermore, adaptive learning support maximizes the potential for student success and fosters a dynamic and responsive learning environment.

Learning in play should support the development of the whole child and allow for active manipulation of learning materials to extend children’s understanding and enhance their interest in the disciplinary subject matter (Bodrova & Leong, 2007).

Table 4. Emergent Theme for Statement of the Problem 3

Superordinate Themes	Subordinate Themes	Codes
Leaners Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection • Improvement • Enjoyable Learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection with students • Enthusiasm for learning • Increased engagement and motivation • Teaching skill enhancement • Interactive learning
Behavior Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased participation and engagement

Learning Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Varied Behavior 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hindrance to learning • Management difficulties • Effective strategies
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student attention and interest • Fostering psychosocial growth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capture students' attention, interests • Great help for knowledge based • Improve social lives • Shows on assessment • Enjoyment in learning leading to remembrance of lessons

Relationship of Interview Responses to Research Question 3:

Statement of the problem 3: What opportunities does play-based learning present for fostering a holistic learning experience?

Figure 3. Themes of Research Question 3 Relationship of Theme 1. Learners

Involvement

The pre-service teachers highlighted the benefits of play-based learning. They noted its effectiveness in involving students and fostering deeper connections, improving teaching skills, creating enjoyable learning environments, understanding students' characteristics, and promoting socialization. They also emphasized that play-based learning enhances involvement, teaching effectiveness, enjoyment of learning, and social- emotional development in students. This highlighted the learners involvement in play-based learning.

Connection

Through play, pre-service teachers can establish meaningful connections with students, as they collaborate, communicate, and problem-solve together. This approach provides valuable opportunities for pre-service teachers to observe and understand their students' learning styles, interests, and strengths, allowing for more personalized and effective instruction. Moreover, play-based learning promotes positive social interactions among students, fostering a sense of belonging and community within the classroom. Overall, the incorporation of play-based learning by pre-service teachers not only enhances student engagement and connection but also cultivates a supportive and enriching educational experience that promotes holistic development and academic success.

“...connecting with students and interacting with them to answer their questions...” PST 1

“...getting students’ attention, winning their hearts, and creating excitement and eagerness to learn.” PST 2

According to Elizarov, (2024), understanding academic engagement has shown that children’s social skills and subsequent relationships in the classroom, such as the quality of the teacher-child relationships, are strongly associated with children’s academic engagement. Moreover, kindergarten academic engagement is an integral part of children’s school readiness, later academic success, and psychosocial adjustment to the school environment. (Estévez, 2021).

Furthermore, academic engagement is a multidimensional construct that incorporates three major aspects: cognitive, affective, and behavioral. Still, it is often difficult to empirically distinguish cognitions and motivations from the associated behaviors and feelings at the preschool and kindergarten age. (Bryce, 2020).

Improvement

Incorporating play-based learning into their teaching practices presents pre-service teachers with valuable opportunities to improve their teaching skills and better meet the diverse needs of their students. By embracing play-based approaches, pre-service teachers can develop their creativity, flexibility, and adaptability as educators. They learn to design engaging and interactive learning experiences that cater to the interests and learning styles of their students, fostering a more inclusive and student-centered classroom environment. Through play-based activities, pre-service teachers also enhance their ability to differentiate instruction, tailoring their approaches to accommodate various skill levels and individual needs within the classroom.

“...improving teaching skills and meeting students’ interests and engagement..”. PST 3

“...improving teaching skills and facilitating student learning through play-based approaches...” PST9

Teaching and learning process can be defined as a transformation process of knowledge from teachers to students. It is referred as the combination of various elements within the process where an educator identifies and establish the learning objectives and develop teaching resources and implement the teaching and learning strategy. On the other hand, learning is a cardinal factor that a teacher must consider while teaching students (Munna, 2021). Additionally, the teachers' dynamics need to be understood by the teachers, and behaviors or teaching approaches need to be adjusted. Again, learning needs, methods or styles of the learners may be different; in this respect, teachers need to understand the need and preferences of the learners and prepare the lesson plan accordingly to meet the learning objective of all learners rather than certain individuals (Kalam, 2021).

Enjoyable Learning

Through playful activities and games, pre-service teachers can spark students' curiosity, ignite their imagination, and encourage them to explore and discover new concepts in a relaxed and enjoyable manner. This approach not only makes learning more enjoyable for students but also fosters a sense of enthusiasm and excitement that enhances their overall engagement and motivation to learn. Additionally, a fun and enjoyable learning environment promotes positive social interactions among students, strengthens classroom relationships, and fosters a sense of belonging.

“...creating a fun and enjoyable learning environment, where students realize that schooling is not just about stress but also about learning...” PST 5

In addition to enjoyment creating learning motivation, motivation to set and achieve goals and tasks can also create learning enjoyment. For instance, students’ ability to achieve goals has been found to be associated with satisfying student experiences (Grace, 2021).

Relationship of Theme 2. Behavior Management

The Pre-service teachers recognized the positive effects of play- based learning on promoting active and engaged student behavior. They acknowledge the potential difficulties posed by chaotic behavior but stress the crucial role of effective behavior management. They also emphasize the importance of finding a balance between the positive outcomes, like increased engagement, and potential negative outcomes, such as disruptions.

Dynamic Engagement

They are motivated to explore, experiment, and interact with the material in a hands-on and meaningful way. Play-based learning encourages students to ask questions, make discoveries, and solve problems independently or collaboratively with their peers. This active engagement promotes critical thinking, creativity, and curiosity, as students are encouraged to explore and experiment with new ideas and concepts. Additionally, play-based learning creates a positive and supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable taking risks, making mistakes, and learning from them.

“...active engagement and participation when play- based learning is used...” PST 3

“...eager, excited, and sometimes chaotic behavior...” PST9

“...excitement and eagerness, requiring behavior management...” PST10

To develop a student-centric instructional module which not only enhances students’ learning capacity but also develops their competencies and skills students, the concept of active learning has received widespread attention. Active learning is the concept of instruction that focuses on using student-centric instructor-led activities and instructional methods (Munna, 2021). Additionally, active learning-based method provides the benefit of increasing students' self-confidence and self-reliance, provides access to prior knowledge, creates the opportunity of better personal interpretation of situations and problems, sharpen the observational skills of students, and lead to cognitive development (Kalam, 2021).

Varied Behavior

Pre-service teachers may find it challenging to maintain order and structure within the classroom while allowing for the creativity and exploration inherent in play-based learning. Additionally, some students may struggle with self-regulation and impulse control, leading

to instances of diverse behavior during play-based activities. It can be particularly challenging to address varied behavior in large groups or when students have varying levels of maturity and social-emotional skills. However, with effective classroom management strategies, clear expectations, and consistent reinforcement of behavior norms, pre-service teachers can create a supportive and structured environment that allows for the benefits of play-based learning while minimizing disruptions caused by varied behavior. Moreover, providing opportunities for students to develop social-emotional skills, such as self-regulation and conflict resolution, can help mitigate challenges associated with varied behavior and promote positive learning experiences within a play-based context.

“...mixed behavior, with play-based learning helping even naughty students answer and emphasizing the need for behavior management...” PST 4

“...varied behavior, with some students showing interest and others being stubborn, requiring facilitation and rules...” PST5

“...happy and excited behavior, but with the potential for rowdiness and chaos, necessitating clear standards and reinforcement of rules...” PST6

“...behavior depends on classroom management, with potential for both positive and negative outcomes...” PST7

Students' behavioral problems are vital to educators as an educational procedure is not limited to leading students' learning and providing them with information. Instead, as a process, it ensures the stability of students' behavior and their emotional, spiritual, cognitive, and social well-being. It is also concerned with finding solutions to possible students' behavioral problems, which may negatively impact their education and relationships with others (Alakashee, 2022). Moreover, ensuring smooth learning processes for students with behavioral problems plays a significant role in setting and enforcing rules to instill conforming values in students (Gharaibeh, 2022).

Relationship of Theme 3. Learning Efficiency

The Pre-service teachers recognized the efficiency of incorporating play-based learning in their teaching, they emphasize that this approach captivates student attention and interest in their teaching. Additionally, they think that the play-based approach is also efficient in fostering psychological growth which encompasses both cognitive development and social skills of the students promoting social interaction.

Student attention and interest

Pre-service teachers who incorporated play-based learning strategies were better equipped to capture students' attention by designing activities that are inherently enjoyable and meaningful. By tapping into students' interests and leveraging their innate sense of curiosity, pre-service teachers can create dynamic learning environment where students are actively involved in the learning process. Play-based learning encourages students to become active participants in their own education, fostering deeper understanding and retention of concepts. Moreover, when students are actively engaged in playful activities, they are more motivated to learn, leading to improved academic outcomes and a greater enthusiasm for learning.

“... you can capture the students' attention, interests, and drive to be recognized by the teacher...” PST 1

“... when you incorporate play-based learning, their attention is focus on their teacher, focus on the lesson...” PST 3

“... gets their attention and makes them listen to our lesson and they also focus...” PST 9

The information processing theories state that paying attention is the first step in the information processing process. As a fundamental component of the mental process, information from outside stimuli initially reaches the sensory memory system of processing (Mehmet & Sadik, 2019). Additionally according to Adolph et al, (2023), playing could enhance the developing brain's capacity to determine which information to pay attention to when and which information to ignore by giving it spatial and time-predictable interactions with the outside environment. According to these two studies playing can catch students' attention and will make them more capable of processing information easily, especially when interacting with their peers.

Fostering psychosocial growth

Play-based learning provides a rich and dynamic environment for students to develop essential social and emotional skills, such as communication, cooperation, empathy, and self-regulation. Pre-service teachers who integrate play-based learning into their instruction create opportunities for students to engage in collaborative play, problem-solving, and role-playing activities, all of which promote social interaction and relationship-building. Through play, students learn to navigate social dynamics, resolve conflicts, and negotiate with their peers, contributing to their overall psychosocial development. Furthermore, play-based learning encourages students to express themselves creatively, build confidence, and develop a positive self-concept, fostering their emotional well-being and resilience.

“...knowledge-based teachings, ... improve their social lives.” PST 2

“...students can learn also by playing ...” PST 10

“...it is effective if you saw the result of their assessment.” PST 4

“...they are more likely to remember the information.” PST 6

“...understand the lessons, ...is effective an if they really understood the lesson.” PST 8

A study by Parker et. al., (2023) states that play enables children to interact with others and express themselves in ways that go beyond what they can express verbally, it is one of the most effective strategies to improve children's psychosocial well-being and learning. Children develop discipline and social skills through play, which creates an essential foundation for their future education and overall well-being. Additionally, Kalkusch et. al. (2022) states that active engagement in roles, encouraging play actions through material or verbal encouragement, modeling play actions, and recognizing and including children's ideas in the play can develop their emotional and social skills. Student in early age are more active when play is involve as it affects their social and emotional skills and many ways allowing them to grow and learn.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the PSTs recognized that students learn best when they are engaged in play and that play-based strategies ignite excitement and interest. They frequently utilized play-based learning, especially when using a deductive approach. The effectiveness of play-based strategies is also acknowledged. Group activities were common context for implementing PBL. The PSTs emphasized the importance of managing and controlling student behavior during play-based activities. The pre-service teachers expressed positive feelings towards incorporating PBL, finding fulfillment and enjoyment in seeing students have fun while learning. It brought joy to both students and teachers as they move away from traditional tasks and witness students enjoying themselves during play-based activities. Effective management was acknowledged as essential for maintaining student behavior and focus during play-based learning.

This suggests that a larger number of pre-service teachers may become more motivated to adopt play-based learning for classroom teaching. To create a positive learning environment and development for students' teachers must establish a positive relationship with their students. The utilization of play-based learning (PBL) in schools might grow, potentially leading to greater satisfaction and the development of stronger student-teacher relationships. Play-based learning might further enable teachers to establish and devise more group activities by integrating play- based learning, hence enhancing student collaboration.

The study found that play-based learning effectively engages students, makes learning enjoyable, and caters to their diverse needs. The researchers observed that pre-service teachers commonly incorporate play-based learning in the motivation and application parts of their lessons, using various activities and strategies to enhance motivation and make the learning experience more interactive and enjoyable.

This implies that the implementation of PBL in classrooms might be able to push schools and teachers to foster active teaching methods. Moreover, additional courses and seminars for teachers may allow them to be more trained and knowledgeable about the incorporation of play-based learning in several parts of their lessons. Play-based learning caters to students with diverse abilities and experiences, enabling smoother progress at their own pace. Through the enhancement of contact between instructors and students, the cultivation of healthy classroom connections, and the promotion of enhanced student interest and engagement, this strategy contributes to the promotion of a more individualized learning approach.

Play-based learning was effective in addressing the short attention spans of primary learners and increasing engagement through enjoyable and meaningful activities. The researchers have acknowledged the positive impact of play-based learning on primary learners' attention, engagement, and learning outcomes. By leveraging the natural inclination of primary learners to play, play-based learning can make the topics or lessons more meaningful and memorable, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes. Overall, play-based learning has the potential to significantly improve the learning experience for all students, regardless of their background or abilities.

This implies that it is important for educators to devise activities that are not only engaging but also meaningful, while also combining play-based learning (PBL), to successfully capture the attention of students and solve the problem of short attention spans. It is necessary for parents to be involved in the process of preparing and nurturing the abilities of their children for their academic pursuit.

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